

SUSTAINABLE PRACTICES AND ITS IMPACT ON THE TRADITIONAL TOY INDUSTRY IN INDIA

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Abstract

Indian toy industry has seen a huge growth in later years due to decrease in imports and increase in exports. Government is taking lot of initiatives to uplift the traditional toy industry through advancement of technology, marketing online, encouraging and engaging parents of kids, building brands, encouraging partnerships. Traditional toy market is seeing a downfall so to uplift the toy market we have to emphasize on the use of bio degradable products and manufacturing eco- friendly toys under different clusters. This helps in mass production and good supply chain practices. Usage of mobile and internet to encourage the marketing and usage of traditional toys is also recommended.

Keywords: Toy, Sustainability, Traditional, Eco-Friendly.

INTRODUCTION

Indian toy industry has seen a huge growth in later years due to decrease in imports and increase in exports. (239%). Indian toy manufacturing companies have increased in recent times leading to decrease in importing toys and exporting toys in recent times. India is gaining lot of importance in exporting domestic toys after UAE and Australia. Government is taking lot of initiatives to uplift the toy industry through advancement of technology, marketing online, encouraging and engaging parents of kids, building brands, encouraging partnerships.

<https://pib.gov.in/PressReleaselframePage.aspx?PRID=1993109>

According to invest India toy manufacturing industry is going to grow 3Bn\$ dollars by 2028. India is exporting most of its toys to Middle east and African countries. Import rates have increased in India from 2023 from 60%-70%.

Toy industry has undergone standardization in 2021 and is working on quality control. The domestic market has been estimated at \$1. 5Bn. It's a labour-intensive industry like dolls, soft toys, board games, as manufacturing companies have a great potential due to its growing demand and competitive cost. The toy industry is a cottage industry. Government is providing support promoting "vocal for local" of National Action Plan for Toys. for bringing together different departments.

In olden days toys were made of bamboo, cloth, hay, clay, jute etc. we can use innovative technology and pave way for better and quality production of toys. Peoples disposable and discretionary income has increased and the toy merchants can tap this part of the income to make INDIA a global hub for the toys.

Channa Patna toys are our traditional toys which are handmade which has unique characteristics. It is made of wood from the Devil tree and natural dyes are used to manufacture using vegetable dyes and resins and pigments from the Devil tree to make it so special. The wear and tear are minimal it is made of good quality wood. Children of all ages can play with such toys.

Kondaplli are toys from Andhra Pradesh. Toys use soft wood, and ecstatic colours. They visualise the rural life including the daily chores, cultivation, using cattle carts.

Different varieties of kites are made in Gujrat and they fly kites during Sankranthi festivals marking the tradition of the west.

Kattputtli are the toys made from stuffed dolls and is predominantly seen in Rajasthan. Thanjavur Golu toys are the traditional toys with a revolving head of a dancer kept during Navratri festival inspired by the chola culture and typically called the "Raja, Rani Bommai".

Asharikandi located near Dhubri in Assam, produces traditional dolls made from terracotta. Banaras wooden toys are made in Varanasi but they get their wood from Bihar which is called Keria wood with complex designs. Natungram, West Bengal, the Natungram dolls are old traditional Indian toys depicting Goddess Laxmi.

Shumee is a Bangalore based company producing eco -friendly toys made of natural wood and cotton and use non-toxic paints and beeswax or almond oil for polishing. It has both online and offline store.

Bloon toys in Mumbai also uses wood and wool to make toys with natural dyes and beeswax, has dinosaur shaped toys which helps in climbing.

Airiro wooden toys are made in Chennai out of neem tree, anti-fungal, anti-bacterial. It makes neem teether, pikler triangle, jungle gym, and balance board. It makes sales online like Amazon, Hamleys etc.

Curious cub is from Punjab and made from wood and fabric.

In India, the Toys & Games market is projected to generate a revenue of US\$1,715m in 2024.

The market is anticipated to experience an annual growth rate of 4.97% (CAGR 2024-2028).

In relation to the total population, each person in India is expected to contribute US\$1.19 in revenue in 2024.

Toys bring in the creativity, innovative capability and development of skill set along with a pinch of entertaining a child. It helps in the all-round development of mental, emotional well-being of children. The toys can help a child when its is not harmful and in turn has a good quality and lasts long with low maintenance.

<https://www.investindia.gov.in/team-india-blogs/karnatakas-koppal-toy-manufacturing-cluster-game>.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

- 1) **Uma Shankar Yadav Ravindra Tripathi** (April2022) opines how the Indian toys industry and the comparison of toys with the global industry by focusing on marketing, export, and sustainable production of toys in comparison of plastic toys.
- 2) **Ashutosh Samadhiya and Rajat Agrawal** explained (August 2021) the problems of Indian toy industry how they were ignored and how government have intervened to sort out the problems.
- 3) **Prof.Ganesh Prabhu** analysed about key market trends the production cluster for the toy industry and problems in toy industry.
- 4) **Avinash Kumar** proposes (2020) the Trend of production and productivity of toys industry in India and way ahead.
- 5) INVEST INDIA emphasises Indian toy industry goes global with 239% increase in exports.
- 6) **Dr. J. Thiagarajan and S. Balakrishnan** 2022 furnishes Opportunities and Challenges of Toy Manufacturing Sector in India

Objectives:

- 1) To understand the overall Indian traditional toy market sectors.
- 2) To understand the usage of biodegradable products in toy industry.
- 3) To increase the customer awareness impact on toy production and the benefits of choosing eco-friendly toys.
- 4) To analyse the Challenges that exist in India's traditional Toy Manufacturing sectors.
- 5) To suggest sustainable practices for upliftment of traditional toy industry in India, through research and development.

METHODOLOGY

When people buy toys, it is generally bought by parents, children or relatives and friends. Therefore, sample includes parents and others who buy toys.

The type of research adopted here is exploratory research that investigates the questions which have to be answered in depth. Exploratory research helps to, establishes relationships between variables.it helps to understand patterns. Exploratory research involves small sample sizes.

Research Instrument

A self-constructed survey questionnaire was administered through the use of the Google Form application.

A pilot study was done taking into consideration 156 respondents as sample size. A sample was collected different parts of the country. Simple random sampling is the method chosen to collect data. Here equal chance is given to each candidate to be selected and questionnaire sent randomly to people The sample included people from different age groups. people chosen included students who would be our future parents 'housewives, professionals etc. Simple random sampling is done so that it can be applied to the entire population.

Challenges in the toy industry:

- The toy industry cannot go in for mass production and sell affordable prices.
- Many people are not involved in the process of production.
- Many middlemen sell products at high prices; government is not giving any incentives.
- Lack of innovation, marketing.
- Lack of awareness about the quality of toys.
- Competition from foreign toy industry
- Paying lot of duties over the raw material procurement
- Implementing quality standards in the traditional toy production.

FINDINGS

1. Age of the individual

155 responses

Most of the sample size included people in the age group of 20-25 years.

2. Educational qualification of the individual

155 responses

Most of the respondents are post-graduates around 72% followed by graduates who are around 27%, so they are well educated and this will help in choosing good traditional toys.

3. Gender of the buyer

155 responses

The sample chosen had more male respondents around 55% were male and 45% were females.

4. Marital status of the buyer

155 responses

The respondents who responded were singles contributing to 76% and married 23%.

5. Buyer belongs to
155 responses

The buyer majority includes people from South India (87%) followed by North India (12.3%) according to the pilot study.

6. Main intention to buy traditional toys
155 responses

The main intention of buying traditional toys by the respondents is because traditional toys uplift the culture and tradition (66%) followed by building creative and thinking skills (41%) felt by respondents.

7. People prefer to buy toys made of

155 responses

People buy toys because they are made of bio-degradable material (50%) followed by people who want to buy toys with a mixture of bio-degradable and non-biodegradable material which infers people prefer traditional toys because they are made up of bio-degradable material.

8. Where do you buy traditional toys from?

155 responses

Most of the respondents around 56% would prefer to buy toys from traditional retail outlets and few from craft mela (43%).

9. Do you buy traditional toys due to

155 responses

People buy traditional toys because they feel that they are environmentally safe and sustainable (66%) and 36% feel because of nostalgia, they feel that their children should play with the toys the parents have played during their childhood days.

10. Eco-friendly toys can help children to understand

155 responses

Respondents feel that usage of eco -friendly toys help children to understand environment and sustainability better, non usage of toxic materials like plastic is harmful and usage of bio-degradable products to manufacture toys is preferred.

11. Challenges in manufacturing traditional toys

155 responses

Challenges what the respondents feel is faced by manufacturing toys is largely given to creating customised products followed by supply chain practices and finally mass production of traditional toys.

12.. What are the sustainable practices to uplift traditional toy industry

155 responses

RECOMMENDATION

How can the challenges be overcome through sustainable practices which can be done by tying up with big corporates and NGOs to sell toys, improving supply chain and forming special economic zones. Creating awareness towards eco-friendly toys and usage of biodegradable material for production, Eco-packaging has to be encouraged. Clusters can help in mass production and supply chain practices.

Channapatna and Kinhal are the major wooden toy manufacturing sectors

Chief minister BS Yeddyurappa 400-acre land. where the cluster is attracting 5000 cr project, attracting one lakh people in the region. Traditional toy market is labour intensive and mostly women are involved in it.

CONCLUSION

Creating awareness among the parents of children by highlighting the benefits of the eco-friendly toys:

- Reduces toxins in toys
- Promotes creativity and innovation
- Reduces carbon footprint by producing sustainable and environment friendly products
- Encourages responsible consumption by passing the toys from one generation to another.
- Help support toy artisans and manufacturers.

Biodegradable toys are natural materials like wood, bamboo, and organic cotton that are free from harmful chemicals and coloured with non-toxic dyes. Emphasising the production process is by using green manufacturing techniques using vegetable dyes, and also using lathe. at times.

These toys are sold in Melas, exhibitions on only certain retail outlets very close to the manufacturing area. Toys are sold during festivities. Toys can be sold by tying up with big giants like Funs Kool, Leo Mattel etc.

Implementing mobile applications and digital components in the traditional toys helps to understand consumers changing preferences, technological advancements and market advancements. Toys are made from sustainable materials, such as wood, organic cotton, and recycled materials so that they are durable. They are safe for both children and the environment. These features have to be emphasised to the customer and usage of plant and vegetable dyes, Eco-packaging has to be brought to the notice of the customer.

To further boost the toy industry, the **Government has undertaken the following initiatives:**

Toy Fair - government organised a toy fair from February 27 - March 03, 2021. to promote traditional, eco-friendly, and indigenous toys and to enhance their local presence.

Toycathon – CSV (Common service centre) And SPV (Special Purpose vehicle) under the Ministry of Electronics and IT with AICTE organised toycathon 2021 a hackathon to develop indigenous toys and games based on Hindu mythology.

Toy Cluster Programme—90% Indian toy industry is unorganised, with more than 4,000 MSMEs operating across the country. Most toy manufacturers are in Delhi NCR, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and small clusters across other Indian states. To streamline this sector, the government announced the 'Product Specific Industrial Cluster

Development Programme' in 2020 to build toy clusters in dedicated SEZs and help them become customised, self-sustained ecosystems catering to export markets. Moreover, the government is also providing incentives at each step, from setting up a plant and facilitating key resources at subsidised rates to incentivising running costs with the single goal of attracting investments and building export capacity.

Several state governments have swung into action and allocated dedicated areas for building toy cities and park clusters. Karnataka is creating India's first toy cluster in Koppal district, designed with the view of housing an inclusive ecosystem of ancillary suppliers and industrial and social infrastructure.

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